

Diels-Alder epoxy CANs and their FRPs

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Background and introduction

Composite materials are great:

- Excellent specific stiffness
- Excellent specific strength
- There is a huge design space (matrix type, fibre type, fibre orientation, core material...)

...except when they're not:

- Complicated to manufacture
- Poor toughness/repairability
- Difficult to recycle (N.B. EU regulation requires 95% of new cars manufactured in Europe be recyclable)

Can chemistry solve some of these problems?

- Covalent adaptable networks (CANs)
- Covalently crosslinked
- Comprise dynamic chemistry
- **Between thermosets and thermoplastics**

Polymer flow facilitates healing, recycling and reshaping

CANs and composites

- A wide variety of chemistries can be used in CANs:
- Diels-Alder (DA) cycloaddition/cycloreversion is ideal
- Forward: 60–80 °C, reverse: 80–140 °C

- Modified DGEBA so that all crosslinks are DA adducts
- Blended into a reprocessable powder

- Vacuum-bag compression moulded into laminates
- Explored processability, repairability and recyclability

Thermal behaviour

- Glass transition occurs at approximately 75 °C
- Two similar systems ($T_g = 60$ ° C and $T_g = 85$ °C)

- rDA-dominant regime at higher T leads to viscosity falling by 4 orders of magnitude
- Viscous liquid suitable for compression moulding

- Capable of repeatable activation with some minor degradation in the efficacy of the DA/rDA chemistry

Self-healing and recycling

Repair

Recycle

Thanks for listening!

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